

Atlas of the 1980-2018 ERA-Interim simulation with the coupled
regional climate system model CNRM-RCSM6

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Internationally recognized for its research in regional climate modeling, the CNRM¹ has developed the sixth version of its coupled regional system model CNRM-RCSM6 to improve the understanding of past and future regional climate variability in the Mediterranean (<http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/spip.php?article1098>). In this work we present an evaluation atlas of the results of a 1980-2018 hindcast experiment driven by the ERA-Interim and ORAS4 reanalyses and observational-based datasets, and we will try to compare as often as possible the results to the observations. This model and simulation are briefly presented in the Research Report 2020 of Météo-France (http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/IMG/pdf/r_r2020_gb_web.pdf, page 20-21), as well as in [Darmaraki et al., 2019]. These are the fruits of a teamwork (the MOSCA team in CNRM, <http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/spip.php?article1035lang=en>), and more widely of the Climate and large scale modelling group GMGEC (<http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/spip.php?rubrique89>). The aim here is to validate the simulation as a realistic representation of present-time oceanic and atmospheric climate. The second chapter will describe briefly the model and the set-up of this hindcast simulation. The third chapter will show the results. Then the last one will conclude and present the next developments.

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Chapter 2

Description of the model and the simulation

2.1 The CNRM-RCSM6 model

Regional Climate System Models (RCSM) belong to the same family as the global Earth System Models (ESM) used in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) experiments, but generally have a higher resolution. They allow to reproduce medium scale atmospheric and oceanic phenomena on periods going from present time hindcast to scenarios for the 21st century. To compose this CNRM-RCSM6 model on the Mediterranean region we chose the up-to-date versions of atmosphere and ocean models available at the CNRM, which are also used for CMIP experiments. The atmosphere model (ALADIN-v6, with new atmospheric physics, interactive aerosol scheme TACTIC, 12.5 km resolution and 91 levels, [Nabat et al., 2020]), the surface modeling platform SURFEX including the land surface ISBA scheme and the bulk FLake model (SURFEX v8, <http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/surfex/spip.php?rubrique12>), the river routine model CTRIP ([Decharme et al., 2019], with deep drainage and flood plains, but still a 50 km resolution), are described in [Voltaire et al., 2017]. The ocean model is NEMOMED12 v3.6 ([Beuvier et al., 2012], [Hamon et al., 2016], [Waldman et al., 2018]), which horizontal resolution is about 6 km, and 75 layers in the vertical from 1 m thickness to 134 m. OASIS3-MCT ([Craig et al., 2017]) is used as the coupler, at a 1h-frequency. The simulation follows the protocol defined in the framework of Med-CORDEX for the coupled hindcast simulations (www.medcordex.eu, <https://www.medcordex.eu/baseline-runs.php>). The Black Sea is not included in the NEMOMED12 domain, its contribution to the Aegean Sea is parametrized as a fresh water flux combining the total river runoffs of its drainage area and the Evaporation minus Precipitation budget over the sea. Finally, as a consequence of the change of model versions and boundary conditions compared to the previous CNRM-RCSM4 model, a tuning phase was carried out, in order to improve the surface radiative and water budgets of the Mediterranean Sea. Some key parameters have been identified in the namelists of the models, and their values moved inside their realistic interval. For ALADIN they concern the cloud radiative properties, convection scheme, microphysics parametrization scheme, cloud scheme, aerosols. As for NEMOMED12, they concern the lateral momentum boundary condition, the treatment at river mouths, the penetration of turbulent kinetic energy below the mixed layer due to internal and initial waves. The domain, orography and bathymetry are presented in fig. 1.

2.2 Set-up of the experiment

The goal of hindcast or evaluation runs is to drive the RCSM with the most realistic lateral, surface and inner boundary conditions in order to (1) evaluate the intrinsic bias of the model in the so-called perfect boundary approach, and (2) study past climate variability and trends.

This experiment called RCSM6-ERA1¹ was described and used in [Darmaraki et al., 2019] to show original results on oceanic heat waves in the Mediterranean Sea. The atmosphere is driven by ERA-Interim ([Berrisford et al., 2009]), with a spectral nudging constraint ([Colin et al., 2010]). The Sea Surface Temperature (SST) seen by the atmosphere is a combination of the NEMOMED12 SST via the coupler and the ERA-Interim monthly-mean SST outside the ocean model domain. The greenhouse gases concentrations, ozone concentration, volcanic aerosol injections as well as aerosols emissions come from the inventories used for CMIP6 ([Sferian et al., 2019]). NEMOMED12 has a zone of buffer in its Atlantic part where a relaxation is operated towards the ORAS4 ([Balmaseda et al., 2013]) temperature, salinity and sea surface height, the latter being corrected in its seasonal cycle following [Adloff et al., 2017]. The ocean model initial condition in August is a combination of the 1975 10-year smoothed average of the MEDHYMAP data set ([Jord et al., 2017]) and the 1970-1980 ORAS4 average in the At-

¹RCSM6-ERA1 is the name chosen for this document; the name of the archived simulation is "TASMAAD12.9".

lantic part. Before the simulation, 10 years of a coupled spin-up have been performed, after a 7-year ocean spin-up and a 78-year spin-up of the river routing model. The rivers are fully coupled from the atmospheric model to the CTRIP model and finally the ocean model, except for the Nile for which a climatological seasonal cycle is applied, with a yearly average of $444 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Erika Coppola, Med-CORDEX community, https://www.medcordex.eu/Med-CORDEX-2_baseline-runs_protocol.pdf) delivered in two river mouths. Finally NEMOMED12 reads a monthly climatology of surface Chlorophyll concentration from 2003-2011 ESA-CCI (Thomas Arsouze, Med-CORDEX community, https://www.medcordex.eu/Med-CORDEX-2_baseline-runs_protocol.pdf).

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Atmospheric evaluation

3.1.1 2-meter temperature

The average air temperature of the simulation, and the difference with CRU on 1980-2015 are presented in fig. 2. The native resolution of CRU is half-degree, and the bias is computed on the AAD12 grid of ALADIN, at about a 12-km resolution. This difference explains the fact that the difference is mainly visible on mountainous regions with a negative bias. This artefact will also be present on the following figures of comparison with CRU. Nevertheless the winter and summer plots show a more global seasonal difference, with a cold bias in winter nearly everywhere and mainly smaller than 1°, and a warm bias in summer except in France and Mid-Europe, as confirmed in table 3.1.

3.1.2 Sea Level Pressure

The sea level pressure is close to ERA5, with a quite small positive bias on the Northern part of the domain, and a negative one on the Southern part (cf. fig. 3). The difference is quite similar in winter and summer.

3.1.3 Precipitation

The 1980-2018 mean of precipitation, and the 1980-2015 bias with CRU are presented in fig. 4 and tab. 3.2. We observe an overestimation of the precipitation on the North of the Mediterranean Sea, especially in winter and over the mountains, an underestimation on the South, at exception of the Algerian and Moroccan coasts. Summer shows a slight dry bias nearly everywhere.

3.1.4 Cloud cover

The cloud area fraction is presented in fig. 5, as well as the 2006-2011 difference with CloudSat-CALIPSO, which resolution is 2° x 2°. It is globally positive, up to 15 percent, except on the mountainous region where a deficit of clouds is observed, as on tab. 3.3, but not significant due to the difference of resolution. In winter and summer the situation is reversed on both sides of the Mediterranean Sea, as seen as well on the seasonal cycle on continental Europe and Mediterranean Sea.

	ANN	DJF	MAM	JJA	SON
Europe	-0.5	-0.8	-0.9	0.1	-0.5
Iberian Peninsula (PRUDENCE)	-0.5	-1.1	-0.8	0.5	-0.8
France (PRUDENCE)	-0.5	-0.4	-0.7	-0.2	-0.7
Mid-Europe (PRUDENCE)	-0.5	-0.5	-0.8	-0.5	-0.5
Alps (PRUDENCE)	-0.8	-1.5	-1.1	0.1	-0.7
Mediterranean (PRUDENCE)	-0.3	-0.4	-0.7	0.3	-0.3
Eastern Europe (PRUDENCE)	-0.4	-0.6	-0.9	0.2	-0.2

Table 3.1: Difference of 2-meter temperature with CRU TS4.0 on various basins mainly taken from the PRUDENCE project.

	ANN	DJF	MAM	JJA	SON
Europe	19	39	28	-8	22
Iberian Peninsula (PRUDENCE)	23	38	25	-11	22
France (PRUDENCE)	14	31	17	-8	13
Mid-Europe (PRUDENCE)	19	39	22	0	22
Alps (PRUDENCE)	9	22	16	-10	14
Mediterranean (PRUDENCE)	23	38	36	-19	19
Eastern Europe (PRUDENCE)	14	37	28	-11	22

Table 3.2: Relative difference in percent of the total precipitation with CRU TS4.0 on various basins mainly taken from the PRUDENCE project.

	ANN	DJF	MAM	JJA	SON
Europe	1	-1	0	3	1
Mediterranean Sea	2	0	3	-1	3
Iberian Peninsula (PRUDENCE)	3	2	4	4	3
France (PRUDENCE)	5	3	4	7	4
Mid-Europe (PRUDENCE)	3	1	3	5	2
Alps (PRUDENCE)	-8	-11	-7	-5	-8
Mediterranean (PRUDENCE)	0	-2	0	-1	0
Eastern Europe (PRUDENCE)	2	0	0	5	1

Table 3.3: Bias of total cloud area fraction with CloudSat-CALIPSO on various basins mainly taken from the PRUDENCE project.

3.1.5 Air-Sea fluxes

The first figure presents the yearly average of surface fluxes on the Mediterranean Sea compared to observations (fig. 6). The panel of observations is described in [Sevault et al., 2014]. It shows that shortwave and longwave fluxes biases compensate to allow a correct net flux. Then fig. 7 compares the downward shortwave and longwave fluxes to more recent observations, yearly averages and seasonal cycles. Concerning the shortwave flux, the underestimation is observed in all seasons except winter, and that can be linked to the overestimation of cloud cover. The trend of the shortwave flux on the 1980-2012 period is correctly represented, as also shown on fig. 8. The downward longwave flux is slightly underestimated at all seasons by the model compared to CERES-EBAF-4.0, while the total longwave flux is surrounded by the uncertainties in fig. 6.

3.2 Aerosol Optical Depth evaluation

In figure 8, the trend of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) concentration, which synthesises the presence of all the aerosols in the model, is plotted as isolines, showing a decrease during the simulation due to a decrease in anthropogenic aerosol emissions in Europe since 1980. In average and compared to FMI-SAT product (fig. 9), model AOD tends to be slightly overestimated on Europe, strongly on the Po basin due to industrial pollution (nitrate), and on the Saudi Arabia's coastline on the Red Sea, and the Western Sahara coastline, both more intense in summer. African dust aerosols are represented, but underestimated on the extreme southern part of the domain.

3.3 Rivers

The total river discharge in the Mediterranean Sea and of the Rhone and Po rivers (main rivers of the basin) follow the observations (fig. 10), the overestimation being due to the absence of dams and irrigation in CTRIP model, and also to an overestimation of the precipitation in all seasons except summer, as we already saw. The total runoff in mm/d into the Mediterranean Sea (without the Black Sea) is situated in the range of the observations, and they are highly correlated. The average of 0.52 mm/d is transformed to 0.19 m/yr in table 3.4. The large spread of reconstructions shows the difficulty to evaluate the total river runoff which flows into the Med Sea, but table 3.4 shows that this element is far from negligible in the total water budget, like the input of fresh water from the Black Sea.

3.4 Water, heat and salt budgets of the Mediterranean Sea

Table 3.4 gives the water, heat and salt budgets of RCM6-ERA5 averaged over the 1980-2018 period. It allows to compare the model to the observations or estimations given in the literature, and to control the equilibrium of the model:

	RCSM6-ERA1 1980-2018	Observations
Water inflow at Gibraltar	0.75 Sv	[0.76; 0.96] in [Jordà et al., 2017]
Water outflow at Gibraltar	-0.70 Sv	[-0.88; -0.80] in [Jordà et al., 2017]
Net water transport at Gibraltar	0.05 Sv	[0.04; 0.10] Sv (ref. in [Beuvier et al., 2012])
Net surface water flux (E-P-R-B)	0.59 m/yr or 0.05 Sv	[0.35 ; 0.66] m/yr ([Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2011], [Pellet et al., 2019])
Heat flux at Gibraltar	6.0 W/m ²	
Heat flux through the surface	-7.8 W/m ²	-3 to -10 W/m ²
Heat content change	1.3 W/m ²	
Salt flux at Gibraltar	1.10 ¹⁶ g/yr or 0.003 psu/yr	
Salt content change	1.10 ¹⁶ g/yr or 0.003 psu/yr	
Evaporation - Precipitation (E-P)	0.94 m/yr	[0.5; 0.88] m/yr ([Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2011], [Pellet et al., 2019])
Evaporation (E)	1.32 m/yr	[1.10 ; 1.24] m/yr ([Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2011], [Pellet et al., 2019])
Precipitation (P)	0.38 m/yr	[0.26 ; 0.59] m/yr ([Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2011], [Pellet et al., 2019])
River Runoff (R)	0.19 m/yr	[0.13 ; 0.23] m/yr ([Ludwig et al., 2009], FOG data [Wang and Polcher, 2019], [Pellet et al., 2019])
Black Sea (B)	0.16 m/yr	[0.11 ; 0.15] m/yr ([Stanev et Peneva, 2002], [Pellet et al., 2019])

Table 3.4: Mediterranean Sea Water Budget, simulation and observations

(1) in term of water content: the net flux in Gibraltar is equal to the water flux through the surface and equal to 0.05 Sv; nevertheless the inflow and outflow through the Gibraltar Strait (resp. +0.75 and -0.70 Sv) are a bit low compared to observations;

(2) in term of heat content: the heat content change over the whole period taking into account the sea surface height is a gain of 1.3 W/m²; the gain through the Gibraltar strait is equal to 6.0 W/m²; the loss of heat through the surface is equal to 7.8 W/m² (taking into account the loss due to evaporation of surface water at the sea surface temperature); this leads to an imbalance of 0.5 W/m² for the simulation, or 0.1°C for this 39-year period;

(3) in term of salt content: the Gibraltar flux is equal to the salt content change and equal to 0.003 psu/yr.

Most of the features are inside the observed range, except for E-P due to the evaporation and the Black sea which are a bit strong, but which compensate to form a correct surface water budget.

3.5 Surface of the Mediterranean Sea

3.5.1 Interannual average of surface features

The interannual average of SST follows closely the observations, as shown in fig. 11, and its trend in °C/decade lies inside the observations in grey, doing better than the previous CNRM-RCSM4 model and other MedCORDEX Phase 1 systems. The Sea Surface Salinity (SSS) interannual average is growing faster than the observations, suggesting that the model was perhaps not at its equilibrium at the beginning of the simulation.

3.5.2 Diurnal cycle of SST

The 1hr-coupling in this simulation allows to study the diurnal cycle of the SST. As a first check, in fig. 12, we compare the amplitude of the diurnal cycle of the SST to the Lion buoy (6.68 °E 42.06°N) extracted from the MISTRALS database, on the 2006-2013 period. The amplitude of the diurnal cycle of the SST is computed as the difference between the maximum of the hourly mean SST between 11h and 18h TU, minus the minimum between 19h the day before and 10h TU. As a first estimation, we consider that we can compare the SST of the buoy (at 1 m depth) to the SST of the model (temperature of the 1-m thick 1st layer). We use the complete days (with no missing value in the observations), and the model value is taken at the nearest gridpoint to the buoy.

Only amplitudes above 0.1°C are kept, and the results are splitted according to the season. The means, standard deviations and correlations are computed on the two series composed by the amplitudes on the same days for both datasets. In average the model simulates realistic amplitudes of the diurnal cycle of the SST, though slightly overestimated in spring (AMJ, $+0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and summer (JAS, $+0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$) and underestimated in winter (OND, -0.3°C). The amplitudes are better correlated in spring (correlation equal to 0.7). In summer, the model doesn't reproduce the extreme values up to 4.8°C . In autumn, it also underestimates the high values. For these two seasons the correlation is equal to 0.3 and 0.4 respectively. The standard deviations are between 0.2 and 0.7 according to the season, while they are between 0.3 and 0.6 for the buoy. Considering that the model grid-point cannot exactly reproduce a buoy behaviour, these results show that RCSM6-ERA-Interim represents a realistic diurnal cycle of the SST.

3.5.3 Surface average

The main differences in SST compared to CMEMS (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>) (fig. 13, left) are concentrated near the coasts, probably due to the nearly half resolution of the model and the presence of upwelling or downwelling which would be smoothed in the climatology due to the resolution and the lack of spatial coverage in observations. Globally they are in a quite good agreement, with a warm bias in summer. The difference in SSS compared to MEDHYMAP (period 1980-2015 only) (fig. 13, right) splits the Mediterranean Sea in two: negative to the West, North (Adriatic and Aegean), positive to the East. The fresh water coming from the river mouths seems particularly visible. The biases are accentuated in summer. The average Sea Surface Height and circulation (fig. 14) shows a correct surface circulation. This is confirmed by the mean 1993-2012 period Sea level anomaly compared to observations ([Rio et al., 2014]) (fig. 15).

3.6 Depth features in the Mediterranean Sea

We first begin by the mean state of the Western and Eastern basins in temperature, salinity and density following the MedW (longitude 5°E) and MedE (latitude 34°N) sections, compared to the MEDHYMAP climatology and the MEDRYS reanalysis ([Hamon et al., 2016], version MEDRYS1v2 here). The MEDW section (fig. 16) shows the presence of a particularly warm and salted vein of Levantine Intermediate Water (LIW) compared to the climatologies (37.5°N , 400m depth), but they compensate to give a correct density. The isopycnal doming around 42°N is well represented. On the Eastern side (MedE section, fig. 17), RCSM6-ERA-Interim shows a presence of dense deep water at 25°E , which can be seen as well in MEDHYMAP, but not in MEDRYS. This suggests a too deep convection in the Levantine basin (as can be seen in fig. 22).

In conclusion, the mean state of the Western and Eastern basins is correct.

Then interannual evolution of temperature and salinity in the whole Mediterranean (fig. 18), the Western basin (fig. 19) and the Eastern basin (fig. 20) are compared to different climatologies. The temperature is correct in the upper layer, overestimated in the intermediate layer, more in the Western, and in the bottom layer, more in the Eastern. But still the trend is correctly represented.

The trend in salinity is overestimated in the upper and intermediate layers, less in the bottom one, where the interannual variability is very smooth. Still the salinity in the upper layer lies inside the range of uncertainties of the reference datasets, which is quite large.

3.7 Ocean winter deep convection and thermohaline circulation

The Mediterranean Sea is one of the few regions of the globe where deep convection occurs, and its role is crucial for the thermohaline circulation inside the basin. We consider the turbocline depth in NEMOMED12, based on a turbulent mixing coefficient criterion using $K_z = 1.10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}$ as a threshold for the bottom of the mixed layer. Figure 21 shows that in winter and as awaited the main region of convection is the Gulf of Lion. Then we plot in fig. 22 the daily maximum of each year inside four basins: Gulf of Lions, Adriatic Sea, Aegean Sea and Levantine basin. In all these basins, the model can simulate an interannual variability alternating strong and smooth episodes. The comparison with the observations extracted from [Somot et al., 2018] in the Gulf of Lions confirms the aptitude of the model to represent this phenomena.

The zonal and meridional stream functions are another way to plot the vertical circulation inside the basin. The zonal stream function is, for a given depth and longitude, the sum of the zonal velocities multiplied by the areas crossed. For the meridional stream function, the same formulation is applied to the meridional velocities for a given depth and latitude. We plot in fig. 23 the average of the 1993-2012 period to compare RCSM6-ERA-Interim to the MEDRYS reanalysis, and then on the whole 1980-2018 period. One can see that the surface overturning cell that represents the Atlantic Water surface and Levantine Intermediate Water circulation is correctly represented in both the Western and Eastern basins even if its intensity is slightly underestimated with respect to MEDRYS in the West and overestimated in the East. With the assumption that MEDRYS represents well the deep water mass circulation, the deep overturning circulation of RCSM6-ERA-Interim is however largely underestimated illustrating the poor ability of this simulation to produce enough deep and bottom waters with nearly no overturning circulation

below 600 m. For the Eastern Mediterranean, this is confirmed by the outflow at the Otranto Strait where one would expect a diving of dense water, as shown in the MEDRYS reanalysis.

The model represents the Eastern Mediterranean Transient (EMT)¹ in 1992-1993, when very dense water was formed in the Aegean and Levantine basin, reaching the bottom, and associated to the outflow of large volume of deep water from the Aegean Sea, but a quite weak one. Indeed, the convection in the Levantine basin in fig. 22 could go down to 3000 m instead of the 1800 m shown, and also deeper in the Aegean basin than the 1000 m we get. It would induce a loss of salinity and a stronger decrease of temperature in the 150-600 m layer of fig. 20, as seen in the observations. The signature of the occurrence of the EMT during the 1993-2012 period is very well identified in MEDRYS (green-blue deep cell in the Eastern Mediterranean in fig. 23 top left). RCSM6-ERA-Interim does not reproduce this abnormal deep circulation even when averaged over the same 1993-2012 period, illustrating a definitely too weak simulation of the EMT event.

Finally the average stratification index (fig. 24, 25 and 26) computed as in [Somot et al., 2018] from the surface to 1000 m, show similar patterns, but generally an enhanced stratification in the RCSM6-ERA-Interim simulation.

¹The description of the EMT and many references can be found in [Sevault et al., 2014], among many other publications.

Chapter 4

Conclusion

The configuration of CNRM-RCSM6 has been exposed, and a panel of results of the 1980-2018 RCSM6-ERA-Interim simulation following the ERA-Interim reanalysis shown. Many plots are extracted from the atlas which is automatically done on the atmospheric and oceanic parts of a simulation to evaluate its behaviour and detect possible problems or bugs (atlas done with the CliMAF python library, <https://climaf.readthedocs.io>). The comparison of the results to various climatologies or observations allow to find this experiment reasonably representative of the atmospheric and oceanic present-time climate. The improvements done since the CNRM-RCSM4 system have been mentioned (new atmospheric physics, interactive aerosols, 1hr-coupling frequency, new ocean model). This confidence in the CNRM-RCSM6 system allows us to simulate the historical period followed by CMIP6 scenarios.

The next development projected is to change the resolution of CTRIP from 50 km to 12 km. The addition of a biogeochemical model, as PISCES, could be considered later, as well as a wave model (MFWAM for example). Finally, the use of the ERA5 reanalysis ([Hersbach et al., 2020]) for the atmosphere and ORAS5 ([Huo et al., 2019]) for the ocean, which both will continue year by year, would allow to continue the simulation as long as possible.

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Figure 1: Domain of CNRM-RCSM6, presenting the orography and the NEMOMED12 model bathymetry.

Figure 2: 1980-2018 2m-temperature (top left), 1980-2015 bias in °C with CRU (top right), DJF, JJA (resp. bottom left and right).

Figure 3: 1980-2018 Sea level pressure (top left), bias in hPa with ERA5 (top right), DJF, JJA (resp. bottom left and right).

Figure 4: 1980-2018 Precipitation in mm/day(top left), 1980-2015 Precipitation bias in mm/day with CRU (top right), DJF and JJA (resp. middle left and right). Seasonal cycle on continental Europe (RCSM6-ERA1 in red) compared to CRU TS4.0 (black line), and E-OBS (black dashed line) (bottom).

Figure 5: 1980-2018 Cloud area fraction in percent (top left), 2006-2011 Cloud area fraction bias in percent with CloudSat-CALIPSO (top right), DJF and JJA (resp. middle left and right). Seasonal cycle on continental Europe (RCSM6-ERA1 in red) compared to CloudSat-CALIPSO (black line) and on the Mediterranean Sea (resp. bottom left and right).

Figure 6: Time series of yearly averaged heat fluxes on the Mediterranean Sea (W/m^2): total short wave, total long wave, latent (top); sensible and total heat flux (bottom); RCSM6-ERA1 in red, observations in grey.

Figure 7: Time series of yearly averaged heat fluxes in W/m^2 and their seasonal cycle on continental Europe (top), and Mediterranean Sea (bottom): downward short wave compared to SARAH-2 and CERES-EBAF-4.0 (a, b, e, f), downward long wave compared to CERES-EBAF-4.0 (c, d, g, h).

Figure 8: 1980-2012 trend of downward solar flux compared to observations (coloured points) from the Global Energy Balance Archive (GEBA) and Spanish network ([Sanchez-Lorenzo et al., 2013]) Contours for the AOD trend.

Figure 9: 1980-2018 Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm (top left), 1995-2017 bias with FMI-SAT (top right), DJF and JJA biases (resp. bottom left and right).

Figure 10: Rhone (up left) and Po (up right) annual discharge (red) in m³/s compared to observations and reconstructions (grey). Total river discharge in the Med in mm/d (red) compared to observations and reconstructions (grey) (bottom).

Figure 11: Interannual evolution and regression lines of SST (top) and SSS (middle) with observations, climatologies and reanalysis in grey; SST trend ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$) of various observations and some other MedCORDEX systems (bottom).

Figure 12: Amplitude in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of the 2006-2013 SST diurnal cycle for the Lion Buoy (x-axis) and the model simulation (y-axis), according to the season. Only values above 0.1° are kept. Mean values and standard deviations are given for each season, as well as the daily temporal correlation.

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Figure 13: Difference in SST with CMEMS (left), and SSS with MEDHYMAP (right), respectively total (top), summer (middle) and winter (bottom).

Figure 14: 1980-2018 Sea Surface Height and circulation

Figure 15: 1993-2012 mean sea level anomaly of [Rio et al., 2014] (left) and RCSM6-ERA-I (right, centered so that the average is zero on the Mediterranean Sea).

Figure 16: MEDW Section (longitude 5°E), 1980-2018 for RCSM6-ERA-I (upper), 1980-2015 for MEDHYMAP (middle), 1993-2012 for MEDRYS (bottom), potential temperature (left), salinity (middle), potential density (right)

Figure 17: MEDE Section (latitude 34°N) 1980-2018 for RCSM6-ERA-Interim (upper), 1980-2015 for MEDHYMAP (middle), 1993-2012 for MEDRYS (bottom), potential temperature (left), salinity (middle), potential density (right)

Figure 18: Time series of Mediterranean yearly mean of temperature (up) and salinity (down) compared to the Rixen climatology shaded in violet, EN3, MEDHYMAP and its uncertainty shaded in grey, and MEDRYS. They are computed for 3 layers (0-150 m, 150-600 m, 600 m-bottom) and the whole column (0-bottom).

Figure 19: Idem for Western Mediterranean.

Figure 20: Idem for Eastern Mediterranean.

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Figure 21: 1980-2018 JFM average of mixed layer depth.

Figure 22: Yearly maximum of daily maximum of the mixed layer depth in the four main basins. For the gulf of Lions, the observations found in [Somot et al., 2018] are plotted in red, and take care that the y-axis is different from the other figures.

Figure 23: Zonal overturning stream function of the MED (left), meridional overturning stream function on the Adri-Ionian basin (right, °N in x-axis), in Sv.; First row: MEDRYS 1993-2012; Second row: RCSI6-ERA1 1993-2012; Third row: RCSI6-ERA1 1980-2018

Figure 24: 1980-2018 stratification Index in m^2/s^2 from surface to 1000m

Figure 25: Idem for the MEDRYS 1993-2012 reanalysis

Figure 26: Idem for the MEDHYMAP 1980-2015 Climatology